

NERC
Environmental
Data Service

Environmental Data Service

A trusted UK facility providing data stewardship services ensuring environmental data of long-term value are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR)

Find data

Browse our extensive data archives.
Search across all environmental disciplines,
or via specific scientific domains.

Deposit data

Making research data available for
long-term re-use supports the scientific
process.

Support

EDS staff are experts in the collection of scientific information, state-of-the-art data management and preservation techniques. We're here to help.

Services and tools

We provide tools that make visualising, analysing and reusing data easier and more efficient.

Data citation

Gain credit for the data you generate. We can make your data citeable and help increase the impact of your research.

www.eds.ukri.org

Our Data Centres

British Oceanographic Data Centre

British Oceanographic Data Centre

www.bodc.ac.uk

Discipline: Marine

Centre for Environmental Data Analysis

SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY FACILITIES COUNCIL
NATURAL ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH COUNCIL

Centre for Environmental Data Analysis

www.archive.ceda.ac.uk

Discipline: Atmospheric, Earth Observation, and Solar and space physics

Environmental Information Data Centre

UKCEH

Environmental Information Data Centre

www.eidc.ac.uk

Discipline: Terrestrial and freshwater

NGDC

National Geoscience Data Centre

www.bgs.ac.uk/ngdc/

Discipline: Geoscience

British Antarctic Survey

UK Polar Data Centre

UK Polar Data Centre

www.bas.ac.uk/data/uk-pdc/

Discipline: Polar and cryosphere